

Fault Location in Power System Networks with Phasor Measurement Units using Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer

Hachimenum N. Amadi, Sopakiriba Maxwell West, Richeal Chinaeche Ijeoma
Electrical Engineering Department, Rivers State University, Nkpolu - Oroworukwo Port - Harcourt, Nigeria

Abstract - The incessant national grid collapse has become a global embarrassment; from 2015 to May 2024 the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN) has recorded 105 cases of grid collapse. Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) are necessary for the extensive use and efficient running of international power networks, the present Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system used in Nigeria does not provide a robust and dependable solution that improves the power grid's real time monitoring and control capabilities. PMU will reduce the frequency of power grid breakdowns and also resolve fault location troubleshooting safely and timely. The optimal placement of Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) is an important requirement in power systems research, particularly for the localization of transmission line faults. This research has proposed a Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MS-GAO) for optimal placement of Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) in Power Systems over the standard Genetic Algorithm (GA) approach used in various related studies. To further validate the performance, the time complexity studies were performed to determine the better technique considering enhanced PMU placement. The proposed approach has been applied to two IEEE power system networks – the IEEE 6-Bus and 14-bus power networks. The simulations were performed using the MATLAB software tool and results compared with the standard Genetic Algorithm (sGA) on the basis of the percentage Classification Efficiency (CE) and the number of trial iteration runs (iters) used per simulation. The results showed that the proposed MS-GAO gave comparable CEs when compared to sGA with 100% CE for 100iters. However, it was found that reducing the iterations to about 50iters resulted in a degradation of CE. Thus, a compromise should be made between the number of iterations required and the level of CE needed in the problem solution. In addition, computational run-time complexity results considering the 6-bus power network revealed that the MS-GAO will give better run-times when compared to the sGA with an average run-time reduction of about 0.5s. Thus, it is recommended that the MS-GAO be employed for a higher power bus networks as the computational demands will obviously be higher using a sGA.

Keywords - Classification Efficiency, Higher Power Bus Networks, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs), Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MS-GAO).

INTRODUCTION

The present state of power systems monitoring and control is an evolving field where the state-of-the-art technologies, tools and techniques are employed in the Wide Area Monitoring system (WAMs) solution of power networks. The Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), Electronic Monitoring System (EMS) and Phasor Measurement Units (PMU) are key components of this solution; however, PMU provides the benefits of faster voltage control speed and sampling rate than the former two [1]. In particular, PMU generally provides the feature of synchronization allowing the time-stamped remote co-ordination of measured voltage, current and frequency phasors among other PMUs in the system. This is effectively achieved using the Geographical Positioning System (GPS) with some other associated electronics.

One of the increasing uses of PMU is in the area of locating faults in power system networks. This very important function requires the determination of precise and highly accurate fault location recording and in a timely manner. It also involves the minimization and cost reduction functions as per the installation and/or placement of PMU for monitoring of the faults at strategic positions in the power network which are very much non-linear and require dynamic programming solutions. Thus, in order to effectively design the installation of PMU systems for fault location in power networks, certain rules have to be met and constraints have to be imposed – this have generally been referred to as the Optimum PMU Placement (OPP) problem and is an active area of research [2, 3].

Nigeria. So, the power distribution networks are becoming highly loaded; so, the issue of protection scheme has become a great concern in most of the injection substation power distribution networks. A number of works have been carried out

in the area of electric power distribution protection and solutions have been proposed to improve the protection of the distribution network [4].

The developed nations rode on reliable electricity to attain and sustain their present status. Today, they can boast of years of uninterrupted power supply which have helped their industries, utilities, hospitals, schools, etc to make life comfortable for their citizens. This means that, we can comfortably say that no nation can move from an underdeveloped status to becoming a developed nation without reliable electricity; no reliable electricity, no development. Sustainable developments have continued to elude Nigeria as a nation due to lack of reliable electricity [5]. Power distribution unit is a device fitted with multiple outputs designed to distribute electric power, especially to racks of computers and networking equipment located within a data centre. Data centres face challenges in power protection and management solutions.

This is why many data centres rely on Protocol Data Unit or Power Distribution Unit (PDU) monitoring to improve efficiency, uptime, and growth. PDUs vary from simple and inexpensive rack-mounted power strips to larger floor-mounted PDUs with multiple functions including power filtering to improve power quality, intelligent load balancing, and remote monitoring and control by LAN or Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) [6]. This kind of PDU placement offers intelligent capabilities such as power metering at the inlet, outlet, and PDU branch circuit level and support for environment sensors. The newer generation of intelligent PDUs allows for IP consolidation, which means many PDUs can be linked in an array under a single IP address. Next-generation models also offer integration with electronic locks, providing the ability to network and manage PDUs and locks through the same appliance.

The existing research has investigated the use of a hybridization of deterministic and stochastic techniques for the localization of power system faults using PMUs. [7] Proposed the use of a novel PMU based fault location algorithm for series compensated lines which obviate a series device model and knowledge of the operation mode of series device to compute the voltage drop during fault. Using the EMTP program, a total of 500 test cases were evaluated considering fault types, resistances, inception angles and locations. They reported increases in error for large fault resistance cases. [8] Proposed the use of Integer Linear Programming (ILP) for PMU based fault location in power system in the presence and absence of Zero Injection Buses (ZIB). They studied the IEEE 14-bus and IEEE 30-bus power systems and reported a much lower PMU count for the IEEE 30-bus considering when a ZIB was applied.

Dual synchrophasor based fault location strategy in the presence of Unified Power Flow Controllers (UPFC) wherein a fault section is identified in the first part using a wavelet-fuzzy discriminator and fault location is determined in the second part using a differential equation-based approach. Compared to wavelet-only based approach and online trained neural networks, their proposed approach was reported to be competitive or better with error margin around 3-4%. However, their approach was found to be prone to higher errors during extreme operations of the UPFC and the fault [9].

The present work deals with a methodology proposed for fault localization in power systems based on Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) for system restoration in power networks following the tenets of an MST as a dynamic optimization problem in the time-domain, model is an efficient route that can be used in planning power network fault locators. This network model also finds applications in telecommunications and transportation planning. [10] One of the fundamental challenges in electrical power systems research lies in the need to determine the optimal solution considering a large number of unique solutions to choose from. This presents additional problems particularly due to the fact that no single algorithm is best as the problem domain tested might equally present its own unique set of issues. [11] Proposed the use of modified Integer Linear Programming (ILP) technique for optimal placement of PMUs and to assure for a full topological observability of power system under intact and critical contingencies. Their ILP technique employed a voltage stability based contingency ranking rule and a graph theoretic approach to modify the constraints under contingencies. Their technique was tested on the IEEE 14-bus system, New England 39-bus system and Northern Region Power Grid (NRPG) 246-bus Indian system and the results compared with three other topological observability based methods. They reported generally lower PMU number using the ILP when compared to the existing models. In [12], the Binary Particle Swarm Optimizer (BPSO) including the depth-of-unobservability criterion and a measurement redundancy objective was used to solve for the minimum number of PMUs needed in a power network.

In [13], the OPP problem was solved using a hybridized approach combining the SA with the Particle Swarm Optimizer (PSO). Furthermore, they exploited crossover and genetic mutation operations to assure for diversity in the particles used for the OPP solution. In another study, [14] introduced a constriction factor BPSO to overcome the local optimality issue and local trapping problem during the search of the solution space for the OPP. [15] proposed a binary based Particle Swarm Optimizer (PSO) including support for zero-injection bus for minimizing the number of PMUs used in a power network.

However, no support for optimizing the fault location function was provided. [16] Proposed the use of Differential Evolution Algorithm (DEA) to solve the OPP problem considering the required (optimal) number of PMUs for full power system network observability and with the Zero Injection Bus (ZIB) included in the constraints formulations.

The Binary Semi-Definite Programming (BSDP) approach has been proposed in [17] for the solution of the OPP problem. This technique produces a set of differing solutions such that the one with the optimal or best approach is selected. [18] Presented dual step strategy where candidate locations are found by iterating line segments in a first step using synchrophasors placed at one terminal end and in a second step where the actual location is found by comparing voltage phasors from junction nodes calculated by synchrophasors placed at both ends. The results on the impact of resistive uncertainties of line parameters on estimated distance were reported.

Currently, there is a growing need to develop and implement better heuristics to solve the PMU Optimal Placement Problem (PMU-OPP) for the localization of faults in power system networks. In this regard, a large number of Artificial intelligence (AI) based PMU-OPP solution techniques have been researched and developed [19]. However, it is a known fact that due to the No Free Lunch Theorem (NFLT), no technique is inherently better than another considering a wide variety of tasks. It is on this basis that this research seeks to make a case for unique solutions to the PMU-OPP for fault localization.

This section details an overview of past research on PMU fault location strategies and in addition, discusses the current trends in the state-of-the-art as it pertains to the location of faults along power network Transmission Line (TL) using PMUs with a specific emphasis on the PMU-OPP. The PSO approach represents a widely used and very popular metaheuristic strategy used in many power systems domains and even in other fields. Thus, it deserves special attention here considering the research works on the OPP problem. A Genetic Algorithm (GA) technique that is constrained in terms of its topology (Constrain-GA) was proposed in [19, 20] for solving the OPP problem. Their proposed approach included topology reconfiguration rules and rules for PMU reconfiguration as well. This involved removal of low-priority buses in the solution space to reduce the amount of non-feasible solutions.

In recent times, a growing number of studies on the PMU-based fault location have been proposed by a number of researchers. These studies particularly focused on the problem of minimizing the number of PMUs scanned in a Wide area

Network (WAN) power system network and hence the costs of installation to solve the generalized PMU Optimal Placement Problem (OPP). [21] Proposed the use of mixed integer linear programming for optimal PMU placement problem in a framework with binary-valued variables and considering small to large scale IEEE power networks. Their solution was implemented as a branch-and-bound algorithm and a polynomial-time solution was reported. The use of limited number of PMUs with synchrophasor data in ascertaining the performance limits of a non-trivial fault localization solution of power system grid is proposed in [22]. Graph analysis following a Kullback Leibler (KL) divergence and a greedy search algorithm is further utilized for evolving different model representations. PMUs data including possible intrusion or cyber attacks on power system grid measurements were also investigated by the authors. Compared to an existing method based on distributed generation, the authors reported better (lower) error estimates using their proposed approach. [23] Proposed the use of hybridization of deterministic strategy comprising a branch and bound method with a Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) approach for PMU based fault location observability of some IEEE power networks.

They used the Genetic Algorithm and Particle Swarm Optimizer (GA-PSO) stochastic strategy to further validate the effectiveness in PMU fault locator. [24] Proposed a Mixed Integer Quadratically Constrained Programming (MIQCP) approach for minimizing the cost of installing PMUs in power network. No support was provided for optimizing fault location. [25] Presented an online GPS time synchronization technique for the location of short circuit point (SCP) faults in power network. Their proposed technique allows reducing the search time and improving the SCP fault location accuracy. To alleviate bandwidth communication demands in PMU based power system network solutions, [26] proposed the use of Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). Accuracies were reported in terms of the Normalized Mean Squared Errors (NMSE), the Mean Absolute Errors (MAE) and compression ratios (CR). Their results showed that their proposed improved SVD solution gave higher CRs compared to traditional methods and their MAE is competitive with the existing ones. [27] Proposed an Iterative Support Detection (ISD) and PMUs for fault location in distribution networks. Their proposed approach obviates the need for fault-type pre-determination and was validated on a 11-bus and a 104-bus distribution system considering performance measures such as fault type, fault location, fault resistance, loss of PMU data and measurement noises. Their proposed approach was found to give better error response, lower bound limits in the case of missing PMU and faster run-times.

Integer Linear Programming (ILP) approach based on the MATLAB optimtool was proposed in [28] for minimizing the number of PMUs used in a power network. Their approach included support for zero-injection bus; however, the approach did not include channel limitation constraints and no optimization of fault location was considered in this study. [29] Proposed a 3-stage heuristic approach for minimizing the number of PMUs used in a power network. Their approach did not include support for zero-injection bus; also, the approach did not include channel limitation constraints and N1-contingency constraints and no optimization of fault location was considered in this study. [30] Proposed Non-dominated Sorted Genetic Algorithm version 2 (NSGA-II) for minimizing the cost of installing PMUs in power network. No support was provided for optimizing fault location.

From the wide body of reviewed researches, there is the obvious fact that there exists no one universal solution to the OPP problem and in the context of fault location in power system networks. It is also observed that the evolutionary metaheuristic strategies such as the Genetic Algorithm (GA) present the best pareto optimal solution [1, 31]. However, one obvious gap in the GA strategy is their computational long execution time which is not a well studied area in the context of PMU based fault localization. This presents a primary challenge and warrants the need for a balance in the solution space between more time-costly but accurate solutions such as GA and less time-costly solutions based on a modification to the selection of fitted individuals used in the solution process – this process is termed Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MSGAO).

Thus, this research thesis specifically seeks to fill this important gap by modifying the structure of GA evolutionary strategy to speed up the computational run times in synchronized PMU power system fault locator schemes using the specific objectives;

- To develop and validate low complexity evolutionary computing heuristics for the optimal placement of PMUs.
- To implement a Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MSGAO) for speeding up the optimal placement of PMUs in a fault locator scheme.
- To compare modified and standard GA heuristic techniques on the basis of:

Computational Efficiency

Computational Run-times

- Develop and apply unique Wide Area Network (WAN) Fault Index (FI) model for use in PMUs based on an approximate Positive Sequence Admittances (aPSA).
- Validate the proposed heuristic strategies on several IEEE benchmark power networks.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

In this paper, the functional methods utilized in the development of PMU based fault localization considering the Optimal PMU Placement (OPP) problem is presented from the first principles. Furthermore, the Evolutionary Computing (EC) approach which is based on a Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm (GA) optimizer (MS-GAO) is presented and validated using a hypothetical Six Bus Network and an IEEE 14-Bus Network – the both networks sourced from materials in the open domain. Then the overall architecture of the proposed system is presented and described.

Materials:

The following materials were used.

- Artificial Intelligence applications
- MATLAB Simulink program (2022a)
- Electrical Transient Analytical Program (ETAP 19.0)
- GNU Octave program (8.4.0)

The data were sourced and collected from open-source data and IEEE benchmarks – IEEE 6 bus and 14 bus power system networks.

Method

State Estimation Technique of Faulted Line(s)

Determining the exact faulted line in advance is not possible in practice; thus, state estimation techniques are normally employed [32]. In this method, a virtual bus voltage state estimator say x , is computed with respect to a corresponding measurement matrix say, H .

Consider a set of power network buses say, D .

Also, consider a bus network measurement set say, z where:

$$z \in \mathcal{R}^D : D = 3d \cdot 4 \tag{1}$$

The measurement set, z , is composed of say two phase-to-ground phasors – the 3-d real and imaginary voltage and current phasors as shown in eqn. (2) and eqn. (3) respectively:

$$z_V = \left[\dots, V_{i_{re}}^{a,b,c}, \dots, V_{i_{im}}^{a,b,c}, \dots \right]^T \quad i \in D \tag{2}$$

$$z_I = \left[\dots, I_{i_{re}}^{a,b,c}, \dots, I_{i_{im}}^{a,b,c}, \dots \right]^T \quad i \in D \tag{3}$$

The measurement model expressions in equations (2) and (3) may be summarized as in equation (4) as:

$$z = \left[z_V, z_I \right]^T \tag{4}$$

Relating measurements with state variables:

$$z = Hx + v \tag{5}$$

Where,

H = measurement matrix

v = assumed Gaussian white noise vectors

A further sub-division of H also allows for the computation of a Linear Weighted Least Squares State estimator (LWLS-SE):

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} H_V \\ H_I \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The sub-matrix H_V is derived from equation (5) and relates the voltage measurements to its corresponding state variables; it comprises of ones and zeros.

The sub-matrix H_I is derived from the equations (7) and (8) as follows:

$$I_{i_{re}}^p = \sum_{h=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^3 [G_{ih}^{pl} V_{hre}^l - B_{ih}^{pl} V_{him}^l] \quad (7)$$

$$I_{i_{im}}^p = \sum_{h=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^3 [B_{ih}^{pl} V_{hre}^l + G_{ih}^{pl} V_{him}^l] \quad (8)$$

And,

$$H_I = \begin{bmatrix} G_{ih}^{pl} - B_{ih}^{pl} \\ B_{ih}^{pl} - G_{ih}^{pl} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

In the context of maximization-minimization (max-min), the LWLS-SE maximizes a likelihood which is synonymous to a minimization operation in the least error sense.

For the purposes of this study, a modified objective function as shown in equation (10) is considered:

$$J_{\text{mod}}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^D \frac{(z_i - \sum_{h=1}^N H_{ih} x_h)^2}{v_{ii} + k_{bias}} \quad (10)$$

By iterating over several trials and across all candidate network measurement buses, the estimated state variable can be computed as:

$$\hat{x}_{LWLS} = G^{-1} H^T v^{-1} z \quad (11)$$

Where,

$$G = H^T v^{-1} H \quad (12)$$

Finally, in order to determine fault position, the Weighted Measurement Residual (WMR) is computed as in

$$WMR = \sum_i \frac{|z_i - \hat{z}_i|}{\sigma_{z_i}} \quad j \in [1, \dots, m] \quad (13)$$

Where,

$$\hat{z}_j = H^j \hat{x}_j \quad (14)$$

The algorithm for identifying the faulted line location is as provided in the following paragraph.

Algorithm: State Estimation Fault Localization Logic

- function FAULT LOCALIZE (TLINE, CURRENT, FTYPE)
- for each time-step k do
- compute WMR_j
- if $\text{mean}(WMRs)|_k \gg \text{mean}(WMRs)|_{k-1}$ then
- Fault 1
- j = index of min (WMRs)
- Faulted Line j
- $I_j = Y_j E_j$
- Fault Current I_j virtual bus
- Fault Type - phases where Fault current $\neq 0$
- end if
- return Faulted Line; Fault Current; Fault Type
- end function

Positive Sequence Admittance Wide Area Network Fault Identification and Localization

Modeling the actual location of a fault in a Transmission Line (TL) is a non-trivial problem that requires the formulation of equivalent power models subject to a given set of constraints. Thus, it is only required that the model approximates the actual values within a permissible error bound. In this regard, better models that closely approximate the faulted point are desired. The Positive Sequence Admittance (PSA) presents a useful and more general approach to identifying and hence localizing fault as it is common to all fault types in addition to it being the dominant sequence component.

Consider the equivalent single TL diagram of a 4-bus power network as shown in Figure 1. An ideal set of PMUs placed as shown. Also shown are the corresponding bus currents, voltages, impedances and fault resistances within a faulted Backup Protection Zone (BPZ).

Figure 1: Equivalent Single TL of a 4-Bus Network [33].

From Kirchoff's Current Law (KCL) and using bus i as reference, we obtain the current injection as:

$$I_i = i_{ci} + I \quad (16)$$

Where,

i_{ci} = the transmission line (i - o) capacitance current

I = the current between buses i and j

The current I , is computed as:

$$I = \frac{V_i - V_0}{Z_i} \quad (17)$$

Where,

V_i, V_0 = the phase voltages at bus i and 0

Z_i = the impedance of transmission line $i - 0$

The voltage at the origin, 0 , can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} V_0 &= V_j - (I_j - i_{cj})Z_j \\ &= V_j - Z_j I_j + Z_j i_{cj} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

By substitution,

$$I = \frac{V_i + Z_j I_j - Z_j i_{cj} - V_j}{Z_i} \quad (19)$$

Z_j = the impedance of transmission line $j - 0$

V_j = the phase j

The shunt capacitive currents at buses i and j can be computed as:

$$i_{ci} = \frac{V_i y_i}{2} \quad (20)$$

$$i_{cj} = \frac{V_j y_j}{2} \quad (21)$$

y_i = the admittance of shunt capacitance in TL connected to bus i

y_j = the admittance of shunt capacitance in TL connected to bus j

V_i = the phase i

Substituting equations (20), (21) and (19) into (16):

$$I_i = \frac{V_i y_i}{2} + \frac{V_i}{Z_i} - \frac{V_j}{Z_i} + \frac{Z_j I_j}{Z_i} - \frac{V_j Z_j y_j}{2 Z_i} \quad (22)$$

Re-arranging equation (22), we get:

$$I_i = \left(\frac{y_i}{2} + \frac{1}{Z_i} \right) V_i - \left(\frac{K_j}{Z_i} + \frac{1}{Z_i} \right) V_j - \frac{Z_j I_j}{Z_i} \quad (23)$$

Where,

$$K_i = \frac{Z_i y_i}{2} \quad (24)$$

and

$$K_j = \frac{Z_j y_j}{2} \quad (25)$$

Re-arranging equation (23) by extracting $\frac{1}{Z_i}$, we get:

$$I_i = \frac{1}{Z_i} \left[(K_i + 1) V_i - (K_j + 1) V_j - Z_j I_j \right] \quad (26)$$

From equations (26), the PSA can be computed as:

$$Y_i = \frac{I_i}{V_i} = \frac{1 + K_i + \frac{1}{V_i} [I_j Z_j - V_j (1 + K_j)]}{Z_i} \quad (27)$$

In a similar vein, the PSAs for bus nodes j and t are:

$$Y_j = \frac{I_j}{V_j} = \frac{1 + K_j + \frac{1}{V_j} [I_i Z_i - V_i (1 + K_i)]}{Z_j} \quad (28)$$

$$Y_t = \frac{I_t}{V_t} = \frac{1 + K_t + \frac{1}{V_t} [I_i Z_i - V_i (1 + K_i)]}{Z_t} \quad (29)$$

To locate the fault, we apply the Kirchhoff Voltage Law (KVL) as follows:

$$V_i - (I_i - i_{ci}) n_i Z_i - I_f R_f = 0 \quad (30)$$

Equation (30) shows that the voltage at bus i , V_i will decrease if the fault current rises (another way to put it is if the fault resistance R_f reduces).

If a fault occurs at say F_2 , from an index point say n , then the capacitive current is computed by the PMU is:

$$i_{ci} = \frac{n_i V_i y_i}{2} \quad (31)$$

Substituting equation (31) into (30), we get:

$$V_i - I_i n_i Z_i + n_i^2 \frac{y_i}{2} V_i Z_i - I_f R_f = 0 \quad (32)$$

Using K_i (see equation 24):

$$V_i \left[1 + n_i^2 K_i \right] - I_i n_i Z_i - I_f R_f = 0 \quad (33)$$

The admittance identified during a fault at bus i is obtained by re-arranging equation (33) in terms of its admittance ratio as:

$$Y_i = \frac{I_i}{V_i} = \frac{1 + n_i^2 K_i - \frac{I_f R_f}{V_i}}{n_i Z_i} \quad (34)$$

This forms the basis of the Reduced (Approximate) Positive Sequence Admittance (aPSA) localization model.

Rather, than perform the expensive computations to decode the fault location as in [33], we approximate its location simpler model.

Consider the absence of a fault; then from equation (34), $I_f = 0$.

Thus, the third term at the numerator can be ignored such that equation (22) becomes:

$$Y_i = \frac{1 + n_i^2 K_i - K_r}{n_i Z_i} \quad (35)$$

Where, K_r represents the ignored fault term defined as a constant; the reason why this is used instead of simply

removing this term is to account for the fault situation at a later time.

The above can be further simplified as:

$$1 + n_i * K_i / Z_i + K_r / Z_i \quad (36)$$

K_r can represent any measurable system parameter at bus i but we choose the voltage, V_i .

Thus,

$$K_r = 1 / V_i \quad (37)$$

From this equation, it is easy to see that when a fault occurs, the voltage V_i is not constant; in proportion to the fault current.

Thus, fault location, n becomes a calibrated function of V_i as:

$$n = (Y_i + K_r / Z_i) / K_i$$

$$n \sim K_r / (Z_i * V_i * K_i)$$

$$n \sim K_r / V_i$$

This implies,

$$n_r = 1 / V_i^2 \quad \text{iff } Y_{i,j} \in \emptyset \quad (38)$$

Thus, it may be conceptualized that when a fault occurs on a line, a line outage persists. From the last model equation, the approximation can be improved by performing an optimization run such that the ideal values of K_r that best represents the faulted location. When n at a given bus is much less than or much greater than 1 ($n \ll 1$ || $n \gg 1$) imply the PMU should be placed at that bus to locate the fault.

This can be achieved using Evolutionary Computing (EC) techniques or more efficient but less accurate techniques based on local search.

Results and Discussion

In this paper the outcomes gotten from the MATLAB, and GNU Octave software simulations were discussed. The evolutionary computing heuristics for the Optimal PMU Placement (OPP) was developed and validated numerically as shown. Also, simulations of a hypothetical model and an IEEE model including real world power system network using the Optimal PMU Placement (OPP) approach is presented. The Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MSGAO) implementation on IEEE 6-bus and 14-bus was simulated in MATLAB and the results shown as Fitness (Cost) Functions. Then the standard Genetic Algorithm (sGA) and the Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MSGAO) were compared based on Classification Efficiency (CE) and their Computational RunTime as simulated in MATLAB and GNU Octave. The Fault Index was simulated in MATLAB using the approximate Positive Admittance Sequence (aPSA). Also several IEEE Benchmarks were validated using MATLAB and

ETAP programs. Fault localization is done using evolutionary computing technique based on the Genetic Algorithms and a modified version – the Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm (GA) optimizer (MS-GAO) as described in the preceding chapter. Associated system parameters.

Simulations using the approximate Positive Sequence Admittance (aPSA) Model

The results considering the approximate Positive Sequence Admittance (aPSA) and the GA as outlined in Chapter 3 for the determination of the optimal bus locations for installation (placement) of PMU during a line outage fault is presented in this section for both the 6-Bus and IEEE 14-bus power networks. The emphasis of the resulting simulation is clearly depicted in this section in the solution of the Optimal PMU Placement (OPP) problem with full observability.

Creating line outage fault on the network to ascertain the fault level and the impact of PMU.

Figure 2: Circuit of 6 bus IEEE Network with Fault Application in MATLAB SIMULINK

Three phase symmetrical fault was applied on bus two at 0.2 seconds to ascertain the voltage profile of the network. As shown in Figure 2, the voltage collapsed to zero when a three-phase fault was applied to the system.

Figure 3: Voltage Profile of bus 2 when three phase short circuit at 0.2 seconds

Results of 6-Bus Network using the Admittance (aPSA) and GA Model

In Tables 1, is shown the simulated result of the Main Program aPSA (6-Bus Network), showing the optimal PMU placement for 6-bus and considering a total of 10 trial runs and for GA population size of 2 and maximum iteration of 100 and it is obvious that apart from the 8th trial run where the GA found only 3 buses - buses 3, 4 and 5 as candidate PMU installation buses, the GA generally recommends PMUs to be installed in buses 3, 4, 5, and 6.

Table 1: Solved Optimal PMU Placement at Different Buses (6-bus)

Trial No.	Optimal PMU Bus Locations
1	3, 4, 5, 6
2	3, 4, 5, 6
3	3, 4, 5, 6
4	3, 4, 5, 6
5	3, 4, 5, 6
6	3, 4, 5, 6
7	3, 4, 5, 6
8	3, 4, 5
9	3, 4, 5, 6
10	3, 4, 5, 6

The fitness response plots for three trial runs (Trials 7, 8 and 9) are as reported in Figure 4. Also shown in Table 2 are the corresponding numerical values (50 data points shown) and the fitness response of 9th trial will terminate earlier than that of the 7th while there is a clear absence of the 8th trial, as shown in the simulation result the Main Program aPSA (6-Bus Network Cost Function). This is attributed to the perfect fitness result attained by the GA algorithm for that particular trial.

Figure 4: Fitness response of 6-bus network for three different trials

As seen in Table 2, it only takes a maximum of 4 data iterations (4iters) for the GA to attain perfect convergence while solving the OPP (see Trial 7). In particular for trial 8, convergence is attained almost immediately making the GA an extremely promising candidate for fast OPP solvers.

Table 2: Numerical fitness values for Trials 7, 8 and 9 (50 data points shown)

Data Points	Fitness Trial 1	Fitness Trial 2	Fitness Trial 3
1	2	0	1
2	1	0	0
3	1	0	0
4	0	0	0
5	0	0	0
6	0	0	0
7	0	0	0
8	0	0	0
9	0	0	0
10	0	0	0
11	0	0	0
12	0	0	0
13	0	0	0
14	0	0	0

15	0	0	0
16	0	0	0
17	0	0	0
18	0	0	0
19	0	0	0
20	0	0	0
21	0	0	0
22	0	0	0
23	0	0	0
24	0	0	0
25	0	0	0
26	0	0	0
27	0	0	0
28	0	0	0
29	0	0	0
30	0	0	0
31	0	0	0
32	0	0	0
33	0	0	0
34	0	0	0
35	0	0	0
36	0	0	0
37	0	0	0
38	0	0	0
39	0	0	0
40	0	0	0
41	0	0	0
42	0	0	0
43	0	0	0
44	0	0	0

45	0	0	0
46	0	0	0
47	0	0	0
48	0	0	0
49	0	0	0
50	0	0	0

Software Platform Validation

The MATLAB software suite while being a very powerful for cutting-edge power systems research studies presents a very expensive and heavy tool to be considered by the engineer and scientific researcher.

This section presents an alternative tool – the GNU Octave (version 8.4.0), that is not just less heavy but free to download and use. The GNU Octave programming language is indeed a roughly equivalent and open-source version to that of MATLAB.

III. CONCLUSION

With the growing interest in Phasor Measurement Units throughout the world and as already implemented in most major cities’ transmission networks; its success largely depends on the PMU-OPP. This research study explores capability of using MSGAO to optimally place PMUs for power networks from the utilization of the optimization techniques in our national grid for full observability will be most economical and greatly improve the efficiency of the grid monitoring and control rate. This research study has developed a novel evolutionary optimizer approach for optimal placement of PMUs in fault location studies using a Modified Sparsity Genetic Algorithm Optimizer (MS-GAO). Both hypothetical power network and a real power networks based on IEEE 14-bus power network were considered in the study of evolutionary strategies in PMU based fault localization. In this research study, it was possible to study numerically, the placement strategies that can be deployed in an actual power system network considering several trial runs and variation of iteration setting of the standard GA and MS-GAO from which it was confirmed the general equivalency of both techniques in the solution process. It was found from simulations that the higher the maximum number of iterations, the more efficient the GA and hence the MSGAO will be more efficient. In particular, it was found that the MS-GAO will do better for

maximum number of iterations of 100iters and above, see figures 4.2 to 4.4. It was also found from the results that the maximum number of iterations for zero based (perfect) convergence is 4iters and 26iters for the 6-Bus and 14-Bus power networks respectively. Computational run-time complexity results also revealed that for the 6-bus power network, the MS-GAO gives an average run-time improvement (reduction) over the standard GA of about 0.5s. Additionally, it was found that the use of alternative software simulation tool – the Octave-GNU can serve as a cost-free alternative to MATLAB, but this comes at the price of increased computational run-times.

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